

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

2
0
2
4

No 4

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

Yashil **IQTISODIYOT** va **TARAQQIYOT**

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:
Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Elektron nashr. 882 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 30-aprelda ruxsat etildi.

Muharrir:
Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, t.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, i.f.d., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri o'rinbosari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, i.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy Majlisi qonunchilik palatasi deputati
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich i.f.n., professor, MIM akademiyasi rektori
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, i.f.d., prof., TDIU YoMMMIB birinchi prorektori
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalendarovna, i.f.d., prof., TDIU Ilmiy ishlar va innovatsiyalar bo'yicha prorektori
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, i.f.d., prof., "O'IRIAM" ilmiy tadqiqot markazi direktori – prorektor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, i.f.d., TMI professori
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, i.f.n., TDIU professori
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, t.f.d., Rossiya xalqlar do'stligi universiteti professori
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, i.f.d., prof., Xalqaro "Nordik" universiteti rektori
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, f.f.d., TDIU professori
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, i.f.d. TDIU professori
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, t.f.d., profesor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Musyeva Shoira Azimovna, SamDu IS instituti professori
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, i.f.f.d., "El-yurt umidi" jamg'armasi ijrochi direktori o'rinbosari
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, t.f.f.d., TAQU katta o'qituvchisi
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, i. f. n., TDAU dotsenti
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, f.f.n., Farg'ona davlat universiteti dotsenti
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, i.f.f.d. (PhD), Alfraganus universiteti dotsenti
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, PhD, Turkiya Anqara universiteti doktoranti
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Maxamatjon o'g'li, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farxod, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi iqtisodiy jinoyatlarga qarshi kurashish departamenti bo'limi boshlig'i
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, i.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, i.f.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, i.f.d., TMI dotsenti
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

MUNDARIJA

Organizational Behavior and Leadership.....	10
Ibrokhim Gulomov	
Baliqchilikda klasterlarini tashkil etishning nazariy asoslari	18
Olim Murtazayev, Muydinov Olim Bekmurotovich	
Оценка состояния привлечения инвестиций в сферу туризма Узбекистана и механизмы управления	24
Арзиматов Бобирмирзо Зокирджон угли	
Biologik aktivlar buxgalteriya hisobni milliy va xalqaro standartlarga muvofiq takomillashtirish masalalari ...	27
Axmadaliyeva Zebo Abdusalimovna	
Aholi yashash joylarida yong'in risklarini bartaraf etish xizmatlardan foydalanish imkoniyatlari	32
Aziz Zikriyoev	
O'zbekistonda ilmiy darajali kadrlar tayyorlash tizimi boshqaruvining tashkiliy tuzilmasi va vazifalari.....	40
Beknaeva Shaxnoza Vladimirovna	
Mintaqaviy turizmning iqtisodiyot rivojlanishiga ta'siri (O'zbekiston turistik xizmatlar bozori misolida).....	45
D. B. O'roqova	
Qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarini ko'paytirishning asosiy yo'llari.....	50
Ibrohimov Boburmirro Baxtiyor o'g'li, Sayfiddinov Sarvarbek Anvarbek o'g'li	
Sanoat korxonalarining aksiyalar bozorida faoliyati tahlili: muammolar va yechimlar	55
Igitov Jurabek Kuzibekovich	
Qurilishda modernizatsiya va diversifikatsiya qilish asosida yangi ishlab chiqarish quvvatlarini oshirish	63
Islamov Ozodjon	
Sanoat korxonalarini innovatsion salohiyatini oshirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	67
J. K. Boymurodov	
Mamlakatda yashil iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari	72
Kadirxodjayeva Nilufar Raxmatullayevna	
BlokchEYn texnologiyalari yordamida raqamli iqtisodiyotni o'zgartirish	77
Karabayev Rustam Zafarovich, Saitkamolov Muxammadxo'ja Sobirxo'ja o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida zamonaviy mehnat bozorining rivojlanishi	84
Layli Mirzayeva	
Xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini rivojlantirishda investitsion resurslardan samarali foydalanish mexanizmlari.....	88
Luiza Komilovna Xaydarova	
Umumta'lim muassasalari sonining ekonometrik tahlilini pedagogik metodlar yordamida amalga oshirish....	93
Ravshanova Muhayyo Maxmanazarovna	
O'zbekiston tarixiy shaharlarida turistik faoliyati shakllanishi va ularni boshqarishning nazariy asoslari.....	98
Meliqulov G'ayrat Abdug'afforovich	
Iqtisodiy rivojlanish va ilmiy tadqiqot rivojlanishining havo ifloslanish darajasiga ta'siri	105
Murodullayev Kamoliddin Sherzod o'g'li, Sadibekova Bibisora Djapparovna, Turdiqulov Farrux Ravshanjon o'g'li	
Hududlarni rivojlantirish va "yashil iqtisodiyot"ni shakllantirishning ekologik muammolari.....	110
Maxkamov Saidafzal Saidkamol o'g'li, Yigitaliyeva Dilnavo Mansurjon qizi	
Ekoturizm obyektining tasniflanishi va alohida xususiyatlari	116
Qodirov Azizjon Anvarovich	
Mamlakatimiz oliy ta'lim tizimida sifat menejmentidan foydalanishning konseptual asoslari	121
Saidqulova Furuza Farmonovna	
Bo'lajak iqtisodchilarning kasbiy kompetensiyalari.....	125
Shukurova Marifat Xodjiakbar qizi	
Ta'limning bosqichlari va ularning inson kapitalini shakllantirishdagi ahamiyati	129
To'rayeva Hurriyat To'yqulovna	

Hududlarda to'g'ridan to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etish dasturini amalga oshirishda marketingni rivojlantirish yo'llari	136
Xamidov O. X., Tojiyeva A. F.	
Investitsiyalar marketingining strategik aspektlari.....	143
Xodjamberdiyeva Dilnoza Bahtiyorovna	
Xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishda investitsion muhit jozibadorligini oshirishga nazariy qarashlar	149
A. Bektemirov, A. A. Abdurahmonov	
Qishloq xo'jaligi raqobatbardoshligini oshirishning ilg'or xorij tajribasi.....	154
Abdulloyev Asliddin Junaydullayevich, Ochilov Narzullo Fayzulloyevich	
Sanoat ishlab chiqarish tizimining investitsion xususiyatlari.....	159
Yodgorova Xalima To'liqinovna	
Turizm sohasi uchun yuqori malakali kadrlarni tayyorlashda davlat va xususiy sherikchilikning o'zaro bog'liqligi tahlili.....	165
Raxmatov Adxam Itolmasovich	
Mamlakatimizda turizm tashkilotlari faoliyatini qo'llab-quvvatlash maqsadida marketing instrumentlari orqali samarali tizim yaratish.....	169
Suyunova Kamilla Baxromovna	
Qishloq xo'jaligida agrokimyo xizmatlar ko'rsatishning iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari	173
Tabayev Azamat Zaripbayevich	
Yashil iqtisodiyotga investitsiyalarni jalb qilishni faollashtirish muammolari.....	178
Xomitov K. Z., Masharipova S. R.	
Considerations on the Problem of Illegal Migration and Human Trafficking	183
Azamatova Gulmira Bayirbekovna, Otarbayeva Guljan Kobeyevna	
Sustainable Development and Environmental Economics in Uzbekistan: A Focus on Carbon Pricing and Renewable Energy	186
Muhammadiyev Po'latjon Ilhomjon o'g'li, Uzganbayeva Dilnoza Toxtasinovna	
The use of Digital Technologies in the Provision Of Utilities to the Population	192
Mamanazarov Oybek Shomurodovich, Inoyatova Durdona Shoxaydarovna, Alijonov Jamshid Alijon o'g'li	
The Current State of the Digital Economy in the Agrarian Sphere: Problems and Solutions	196
Babadjanov Abdirashid Musayevich	
Behavioral Theory of the Firm.....	201
Egamberdieva Oydin Abror qizi	
The Role of Information Technologies in Increasing the Capitalization of Commercial Banks	207
Egamova Makhfurat Esanovna	
Финансовые риски в исламском финансировании для внедрения в Республики Узбекистан	211
Абдуллоев Фуркат Олимджонович	
Совершенствование методологии экспертизы инвестиционных проектов	216
Бекимбетова Гулнора Маратовна	
Методические подходы к формированию механизмов стратегического управления развитием химической отрасли.....	223
Бибутова Шахло Саъдуллаевна	
Меры по снижению доли теневой экономики в стране.....	228
Махмудова Юлдузхон Бахромжон кизи, Сафаров Гиёсиддин Абдуллаевич ўгли	
Формирование национальной инновационной системы – одна из приоритетных задач повышения конкурентоспособности Республики Узбекистан	232
Н. М. Махмудов, А. А. Алиев, З. А. Мирзоев	
Мониторинг и анализ современного состояния и развития промышленности в Узбекистане.....	237
Назарова Раъно Рустамовна, Исмоилова Малика Дилшодовна	
Цифровая платформа как инструмент трансформации бизнес-процессов.....	243
Раупов Жамшид Рашидович	
Роль применения ключевых показателей эффективности труда на предприятиях.....	249
Рахматуллаева Шахноза Хамидовна	

Влияние цифровой трансформации на инвестиционную привлекательность Узбекистана.....	255
Саиткамоллов Муҳаммадхожа Сабирходжа угли, Маркабаева Жансая Айбек кызы	
Организация и координация методической помощи при управлении педагогическими кадрами	261
Хакимова Майя Юрьевна	
Интеграция узбекистана в мировое экономическое содружество путем унификации бухгалтерского учета на основе МСФО	266
Зарипова Саёхат Зафаровна	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan investitsiya loyihalarini moliyalashni rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari.....	271
Abduqodirova Ozoda Anvarjon qizi	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan jismoniy shaxslarga ajratilgan kreditlarning joriy tahlili.....	276
Abdusalomov Jaxongir O'ktam o'g'li	
Globalashuv sharoitida mamlakatimizda sug'urta bozorini raqamlashtirishning ahamiyati	282
Anvarova Z.	
The Role of Parents and Teachers in Promoting a Healthy Lifestyle in Children.....	286
Axtamov Djamshed Baxromovich	
A Study of the Importance of Green Economy in Uzbekistan Sustainable Economic Development and its Measurement Indicators in Relation to Environment.....	291
Ataniyazova Maksuda Baltayevna, Tairova Zarnigor Mammot qizi	
Konsolidatsiyalashgan moliyaviy hisobot tuzishning zarurligi.....	296
Avazov Iloxom Ravshanovich	
Foydani soliqqa tortish obyekti sifatidagi iqtisodiy tarkibi.....	301
Axrorov Zarif Oripovich	
Surxondaryo viloyatida aholining uy-joy bilan ta'minlanganlik darajasini tahlili.....	309
Ibragimov Qobil To'xtamishovich	
Review of Methodological Approaches to Enterprises Financial Condition Analysis.....	314
Ismailova Maxbuba Mirxalilovna	
Innovatsion rivojlanish sharoitida xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini tasniflanishining nazariy va ilmiy asoslari.....	319
Masharipova Manzura Alimbayevna	
Korxonalarda benchmarking strategiyalarini qo'llashning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlari.....	325
Narziyeva Dilafiruz Muxtorovna	
Davlat budjetining soliqsiz daromadlari shakllanishini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	330
O'ktamova Nargiza Narzulla qizi	
Mamlakatimizda sanoat ishlab chiqarishi korxonalarining rivojlanish holati tahlili.....	334
Olimov Maqsudjon Komiljon o'g'li	
Moliyaviy natijalar to'g'risidagi hisobotni moliyaviy hisobotning xalqaro standartlar talablari asosida tuzish.....	339
Pardayeva Zulfizar Alimovna	
Raqamlashtirish sharoitida qo'shma korxonasi faoliyatining tahlili.....	343
Rashidov Jamshid Xamidovich	
Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikning rivojlanishida oilaviy tadbirkorlikning o'rni.....	348
Raximov Baxromjon Ibroximovich, Saloxiddinov Zuxriddin Nuriddin o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida xizmat ko'rsatishning ilmiy asoslari.....	352
Suyunov Asror Baxtiyorovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida telekommunikatsiya sohasini rivojlantirish ilmiy asoslari.....	356
Toshmatov Salohiddin Zayniddinovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida innovatsiyalarni joriy etishning huquqiy masalalari.....	360
Turg'unov Saloxiddin Jamol o'g'li, Mirzayeva Mohidil Vohidovna	
Zamonaviy sharoitlarda korxonalarining moliyaviy baqarorligini yaxshilash masalalari	366
Usmanova Guljahon Ulug'bek qizi	
Franshizalarni jalb qilishda davlat boshqaruvi tizimida marketing tadqiqotlarining ahamiyati	371
Xodjayev Anvar Rasulovich	

Transport Decarbonization Strategy.....	377
Yarashova Vasila Kamalovna, Muradov Bekzod Xidirnazar ugli	
Temir yo'l transportida ishlab chiqarish faoliyatining iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish	382
Yermatova Dilnoza Axmadjonovna	
Iqtisodiyotda davlat ishtirokini qisqartirish va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish istiqbollari	387
Yuldashev Xusniddin Abdullayevich	
Issiqlik ta'minoti xizmatlarini ko'rsatish samaradorligi va sifatini baholash ko'rsatkichlari tizimi.....	390
Abdulaziz Abdumo'minovich Matro'ziyev	
Issiqlik ta'minoti xizmatlari sifatiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar va ularni baholash	394
Abdulaziz Abdumo'minovich Matro'ziyev	
Jismoniy shaxslarning mol-mulkiga soliq solishni takomillashtirish.....	399
Abdullayev Zafarjon Alijonovich, Zaydullayev Abduhabib Boliqul o'g'li	
Sug'urta tashkilotlarida hisob siyosatini ishlab chiqishning ahamiyati.....	404
Abduraimova Maftunaxon Axmatovna	
Bank risklarini boshqarishning xalqaro tajribalari.....	409
Abdurasulov Jaxongir Abduvaliyevich	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlari ijtimoiy ma'sulligini ta'minlash mexanizmining amal qilish darajasi.....	416
Bayisbayev Javlon Nurlanovich	
Qishloq aholisining qishloq xo'jaligida bilim va innovatsiyalarni o'zlashtirishga ta'sir etuvchi omillarni iqtisodiy baholash (Samarqand viloyati misolida).....	421
Bozorova Lobar Nuralevna	
Направления совершенствования инновационных стратегий в деятельности промышленных предприятий.....	427
Дониерова Зухрабону Алишер кизи	
Mol-mulk solig'ining korxonalar faoliyatiga ta'siri.....	432
Qudiyarov Kishibay Ramatullayevich	
Banklar reytingini aniqlash va barqarorligini ta'minlashning ustuvor yo'nalishlari.....	438
Maxmudov Omon Tuxtayevich	
Iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash sharoitida tijorat banklarining aktiv va passiv operatsiyalarini innovatsion usullar orqali boshqarishni takomillashtirish	442
Mo'minova Ma'suda Baxtiyarovna	
Auditorlik tekshiruvini dasturiy ta'minot asosida tashkil etish: muammo va yechimlar.....	447
Nazarova Kamola Sattoral qizi	
Ishlab chiqarish infratuzilmasini rivojlantirishning davlat tomonidan tartibga solish konsepsiyasi.....	453
Normurodov Xusan Eshmaxmatovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikning ahamiyati hamda uni rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	460
Nurullayeva Shaxnoza, Saydullayeva Saodat	
Tijorat banklari inson kapitali samaradorligini baholashda KPI ko'rsatkichlaridan foydalanish mexanizmlari	467
Turaeva Mastura Kurbanovna	
Сущность и особенности инвестиционно-строительного процесса	471
А. Бектемиров, Б.М.Абдувалиев	
Tijorat banklarida muammoli kreditlarni boshqarishning dolzarb masalalari.....	478
Saidov Hayotjon Raxmatulloevich	
Tijorat banklarida kredit operatsiyalari hisobini takomillashtirish.....	482
Sa'dullayeva Asalxon Muzaffarovna	
Ko'p tarmoqli fermer xo'jaliklarining raqobatbardoshlikni baholash usullari	485
Abdulloyev Asliddin Junaydullayevich, Teshayev Mirolim Djumayevich	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlarida soliq yukini optimallashtirish mexanizmi	490
To'xsanov Quدراتillo Nozimovich	

Davlat sektorida ichki audit tadbirlarini umumiy rejalashtirish	495
Xamidova Z. U.	
Aholi moliyaviy savodxonligini oshirish va uning ahamiyati.....	501
Xudayarova Xurshida Abdunazarovna	
Kambag'allikni qisqartirishning xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	505
Xudoyberdiyev Jamshid Juraboy o'g'li	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida buxgalteriya hisobi va ichki auditni takomillashtirish	511
Shaymatova Nargiza Ashurovna	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida sug'urta xizmatlari.....	516
Shodmonova Odina G'ofur qizi	
Fuqarolar davlat pensiya ta'minoti tizimining amaldagi holati tahlili.....	520
Sholdarov Dilshod Azimiddin o'g'li	
Aholiga bank xizmatlari ko'rsatishning ijtimoiy ahamiyati.....	525
Eldor Uskanov	
Innovatsion boshqaruvning ilg'or xorijiy tajribalari	530
Yusupova Jamila Karamatdinovna	
Neft-gaz korxonalarini moliyaviy-iqtisodiy faoliyati natijalari tahlili ("O'ZBEKNEFTGAZ" AJ misolida)	534
Umurzoqov Jamoliddin Sherbekovich	
Korxonalarda savdo marketing faoliyati samaradorligini baholash.....	541
Sobirov Azizbek Avzbekovich	
Moliyaviy firibgarliklarga qarshi kurashishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish imkoniyatlari.....	548
Gadaev Ismat Yadgarovich	
Hududlarda islom iqtisodiyoti tamoyillari asosida amalga oshirilgan investitsion loyihalar: to'siqlar va yechimlar	551
Irgasheva Gulbahor Sodiqovna	
O'zbekistonda investitsiyalardan samarali foydalanish asosida oziq-ovqat sanoati samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari.....	554
Kobilova Nasiba Xurramovna	
Foreign Economic Relations as a Factor of Effective Functioning of the Economy	561
Bakhodurova Sulkhya Azizkhodjaevna, Li Marina Rudolfovna, Mukhtarova Donata Ravshanbekovna, Romashkin Roman Anatolyevich	
Modern Approaches to the Organization and Development of the Consumer Services Market.....	566
Musyeva Shoira Azimovna	
Ishlab chiqarish siklini qisqartirishning iqtisodiy samaradorligi.....	570
Odina Nabiyevna Tuychiyeva, Nazarova Latofat Toirjon qizi	
Asalarichilik mahsulotlari bozorida marketing strategiyasini amalga oshirish.....	575
Rashidova Xadicha Tursunalievna	
Iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash sharoitida bank faoliyatini iqtisodiy-matematik modellashtirish yo'llari	581
Raxmanov Mexridin Sindarovich	
Korporativ boshqaruv amaliyoti bo'yicha hisobot tuzish bo'yicha xorijiy tajriba.....	586
Tashmatov Rustam Xusanovich	
Iqtisodiyotda davlat ishtirokini qisqartirish va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish istiqbollari	592
Yuldashev Xusniddin Abdullayevich	
Iqtisodiyotda turizm o'rnini statistik baholash uslubiyoti.....	595
Zilola Jumanova	
Финансовые риски в исламском финансировании для внедрения в Республики Узбекистан	602
Абдуллоев Фуркат Олимджонович	
Блокчейн-технология и информационная безопасность в цифровой экономике Узбекистана.....	607
Кадиров Алишер Исмаилович	
Цифровая платформа как инструмент трансформации бизнес-процессов	611
Раупов Жамшид Рашидович	

O'zbekistonda zamonaviy kabel va sim mahsulotlari ishlab chiqaruvchi korxonalar faoliyatiga nazar.....	617
Rashidova Odina Olimjon qizi	
Современные тенденции развития валютных отношений в Узбекистане	622
Камалов Камолалдин Кахрамонович	
Sug'urta sohasining O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotidagi o'rni	626
Sharobiddinov Akramjon Goyibbayevich	
Kichik biznes va tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishning xorij tajribasi va undan O'zbekistonda foydalanish yo'nalishlari	630
Fayziyeva Aziza Azamat qizi	
Modeling the Stackelberg strategy in a linear model (linear city) Hotteling.....	635
Musayeva Shaira Azimovna, Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna	
Mulkning kapitallashuvi darajasini iqtisodiy jihatdan amalga oshirish samaradorligini baholash uslublari.....	644
Norboyev Odil Abrayevich	
Tijorat banklarining kredit portfelini amaliy holati va ekonometrik tahlillari: ATB "Aloqabank" misolida.....	649
Norov Akmal Ruzimamatovich, Norova Nozima Nabiyeвна	
O'zbekistonda "yashil iqtisodiyot" muhitida kreditlash va moliyalashtirish imkoniyatlari	654
Taxir Urkinbayev	
Budjet tashkilotlarida ichki nazorat tizimini tashkil qilishning xususiyatlari.....	658
Abduraxmanov Ramazon Abdullayevich	
Chinese Commercial Banks Experience in Asset Diversification	663
Uktamova Nozima Narzulla kizi	
Sanoat taraqqiyotida ishlab chiqarish korxonalarini ustuvor rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	667
Yadgarov Akram Akbarovich	
Анализ деятельности коммерческих банков Узбекистана по кредитованию физических лиц.....	673
Базарова Нигора Равшановна	
Mahalliy va xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishning innovatsion jarayonlarga ta'sirini baholash.....	684
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida innovatsiyalarning iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari	689
Kuziyeva Nargiza Ramazanovna, Xusanov Faxriddin Jamoliddin o'g'li	
Tashqi mehnat migratsiyasi.....	694
O. N. Djurayev	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotda sanoat tarmog'ining davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanishini baholash	699
Otaboyeva Dildora	
Nobank kredit tashkilotlarining moliyaviy xizmatlari sifatini oshirishning xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi	705
Raimov Xurshid Muxtorovich	
Tijorat banklarida moliyaviy injiniringni qo'llash istiqbollari	711
Saipnazarov Sherbek Shaylavbekovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi moliya bozorida tijorat banklari faoliyati: muammo va yechimlar	716
Toymuxamedov Ibroxim Rixsiboevich, Jumaev Islombek Akram o'g'li	
Agrar ta'lim tizimida boshqaruv samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari	723
Boltayev Nurali Shiramatovich, Beglayev Uchqun Xurramovich, Abdiyev Izzat Risqiboyevich	
O'zini o'zi band qilgan shaxslardan olinadigan soliqlarni takomillashtirish orqali yashirin iqtisodiyotni jilovlash masalalari	731
Davranov Iskandar Jumayevich	
Iqtisodiy konsentratsiyalarni tartibga solish va nazorat qilishni takomillashtirish.....	738
Luqmanov Sharifxon A'zam o'g'li	
Role of Private and Public Kindergartens in Early Childhood Development	744
Makhmudova Munisakhon Abbos qizi	
"Yashil" enegriya quvvatlarini barpo etish iqtisodiy barqarorlikni ta'minlash asosi sifatida.....	749
Muminova Elnoraxon Abdukarimovna, Umarova Dilnoza Oybek qizi	
Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarda CVP-tahlilni tashkil etishning muammoli jihatlari	754
Qlichev Baxtiyor Pardayevich	

Korxonada likvidlik riskini minimallashtirish orqali uning moliyaviy barqarorligini saqlab qolish	759
Latipova Shaxnoza Maxmudovna	
Развитие международных торгово-экономических связей Республики Узбекистан	766
Ким Татьяна Валерьевна, Гофуржонова Шахрибону Бахромжон кизи	
Kapital qurilishni boshqarish samaradorligini oshirishning dolzarb masalalari	774
A. Bektemirov, M. U. Sarimsoqov	
O'zbekiston mehnat bozorida yoshlarning ish bilan bandlik darajasini oshirish.....	780
Mambetjanov Qahramon Qurbandurdiyevich, Bahromov Shahzod Fazliddinovich	
Роль имиджа в улучшении инвестиционной привлекательности высших учебных заведений.....	787
Жанзаков Бекзот, Жонузоков Мирзабек	
Innovatsion kichik tadbirkorlikni qo'llab-quvvatlash bo'yicha xorij tajribasi va uni mamlakat iqtisodiyotida qo'llash imkoniyati.....	795
Toshaliyeva Saodat Toxirovna, Eshqulova Dilorom Abduravupovna	
Перспективы развития банковского сектора в Узбекистане для иностранных туристов	802
Муминов Шахзод Низомиддинович, Каримова Азиза Махомадризоевна	
Innovatsion faoliyat moliyaviy modellari va mexanizmlarini rivojlantirishning konseptual asoslari	806
Ruzibayeva Nargiza Xakimovna	
Qishloq xo'jaligi tarmoqlarini innovatsion rivojlantirish bo'yicha xorijiy tajribalar va ulardan respublikamizda samarali foydalanish yo'llari	814
Ishniyazov Baxrom Normamatovich	
Turistik xizmatlarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va marketing tadqiqotlari.....	819
Berdiqulova Iroda Rayimqulovna	
Qoraqalpog'iston qishloq xo'jaligi: asosiy muammolar va rivojlanishining ustuvor yo'nalishlari	823
Yeshimbetov Uktamjon Xudaybergenovich	
Iqtisodiyotning erkinlashtirilishi sharoitlarida kichik biznes sektori rivojlanishining imkoniyatlari.....	832
Botirova R. A., Sirojiddinov I. Q.	
Kriptovalyuta va blokcheyn tadqiqotlari: tendensiyalar va istiqbollar	835
Berdiqulov Jurabek	
Bank risklarni monitoring qilish tizimini takomillashtirish	837
Hamroyev Sherzod Axtamovich	
O'zbekiston hududlariga xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilishda ko'p qavatli "yashil" fermer xo'jaliklarini tashkil etishning ahamiyati	843
Turdimuratova Aziza Alisherovna	
Surxondaryo viloyatining mahalliy budjet daromadlarini oshirish yo'llari va uni arima modeli asosida prognozlash.....	846
Abdunazarova Shahnoza Norqo'chqor qizi	
Qishloq xo'jaligi tarmog'ining mamlakat iqtisodiyotidagi o'rni va undagi tarkibiy o'zgarishlarni statistik baholash.....	856
Zakirova Umida Maxamadaminovna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalarining ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy mohiyati	863
Pardayev Jamshid Muzaffarovich	
Turizm bozorini rivojlantirishda mehnat bozorining tutgan o'rni va ahamiyati	872
Berdiqulova Iroda Rayimqulovna, Berdikulov Jurabek	
Проблемы расчета определения и планирования прибыли предприятий в условиях модернизации экономики	876
Алиева С.С.	

ROLE OF PRIVATE AND PUBLIC KINDERGARTENS IN EARLY CHILDHOOD DEVELOPMENT

Makhmudova Munisakhon Abbos qizi

Tashkent State University of Economics, assistant teacher in Business Administration department

Abstract: This article analyzes research that builds on successes and lessons learned from previous strategies and incorporates new initiatives to address emerging needs and challenges. Overall, Uzbekistan's education sector has made significant progress in expanding access and improving quality, but there is still work to be done, particularly in terms of student inclusion and gender equality. Continuous support from the state, strategic planning and international cooperation to further improve the educational system of Uzbekistan and expand its institutional capabilities for a bright future are of priority.

Key words: Demographic, urban areas, preschool, enrollment, UNICEF, reforms, teacher, training, parents.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada oldingi strategiyalardan olingan muvaffaqiyatlar va saboqlarga asoslanib, paydo bo'ladigan ehtiyoj va muammolarni hal qilish uchun yangi tashabbuslarni o'z ichiga olgan tadqiqotlar tahlil qilingan. Umuman olganda, O'zbekiston ta'lim sohasi foydalanish imkoniyatlarini kengaytirish va sifatni oshirishda sezilarli muvaffaqiyatlarga erishdi, biroq, ayniqsa, o'quvchilarni qamrab olish va gender tenglik bo'yicha hali qilinishi kerak bo'lgan ishlar mavjud. Davlat tomonidan doimiy qo'llab-quvvatlash, strategik rejalashtirish va xalqaro hamkorlikda O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimini yanada takomillashtirish va yorqin kelajak uchun institutsional imkoniyatlarini kengaytirish ustuvor ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: Demografik, shaharlar, maktabgacha ta'lim, ro'yxatga olish, UNICEF, islohotlar, o'qituvchi, trening, ota-onalar.

Аннотация: В этой статье анализируются исследования, основанные на успехах и уроках, извлеченных из предыдущих стратегий, и включают новые инициативы для решения возникающих потребностей и проблем. В целом, сектор образования Узбекистана добился значительного прогресса в расширении доступа и повышении качества, но предстоит еще многое сделать, особенно в плане вовлечения студентов и гендерного равенства. Постоянная поддержка со стороны государства, стратегическое планирование и международное сотрудничество в целях дальнейшего совершенствования системы образования Узбекистана и расширения ее институциональных возможностей для светлого будущего имеют приоритетное значение.

Ключевые слова: Демография, городские районы, дошкольные учреждения, набор, ЮНИСЕФ, реформы, учителя, обучение, родители.

INTRODUCTION

The Government of Uzbekistan has demonstrated a consistent commitment to the education sector since gaining independence. While the primary focus initially centered on achieving and maintaining high enrollment rates in the General Secondary Education sector, recent years have seen a shift towards a more comprehensive approach to education, in alignment with global Sustainable Development Goals for Education. Uzbekistan has achieved remarkable success in ensuring near-universal enrollment in primary and secondary education, meeting the targets set by the Millennium Development Goals (MDG) by 2015. The average number of years of schooling has remained stable at around 11-12 years over the past three decades, reflecting the government's dedication to providing access to education for all. However, recognizing the evolving global landscape and the need for broader improvements in education quality and access, Uzbekistan has embarked on ambitious reforms. In 2017, the government introduced the National Action Strategy on Five Priority Development Areas 2017-2021, with education development being one of the key focus areas. This strategy laid the foundation for comprehensive reforms across all sub-sectors of education. One significant initiative was the development of the Education Sector Plan (ESP) 2019-2023 in consultation with stakeholders and international partners like UNICEF. The ESP outlined sectoral priorities and action plans for the government to implement over the specified period¹.

1 <https://www.unicef.org/uzbekistan/media/5671/file/Partnership%20Compact%20for%20Education%20reform.pdf>

In tandem with economic reforms, the government has pursued transformative measures in the education sector, attracting investment from bilateral agencies and conducting numerous studies to address sectoral challenges. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, who assumed office for a second term following the presidential elections in October 2021, reaffirmed the government's commitment to prioritizing quality education and development. In his address, President Mirziyoyev underscored the importance of developing a new National Education Programme to further advance education quality and access across Uzbekistan. This programme is expected to build upon the successes and lessons learned from previous strategies while incorporating new initiatives to address emerging needs and challenges. Overall, Uzbekistan's education sector has made significant strides in expanding access and improving quality, but there is still work to be done to meet the ambitious targets set forth in the SDGs. With continued government support, strategic planning, and collaboration with international partners, Uzbekistan is poised to further enhance its education system and empower its citizens for a brighter future. In light of recent developments in Uzbekistan and the government's initiative to develop a "New Education Programme," it is imperative to conduct a comprehensive Education Sector Analysis (ESA). This analysis aims to thoroughly assess the education sector, including systemic reforms, interventions, and outcomes achieved in recent years. By identifying areas for priority action and potential strategies, the ESA will inform the review and modification of the Education Sector Plan (ESP) 2019-2023 to align with current priorities and goals. The ESA will primarily focus on three key sub-sectors of education: Preschool Education (PSE), General Secondary Education (GSE), and Higher or Tertiary Education (HE). Within these sub-sectors, the analysis will examine the policy areas and strategic priorities outlined in the ESP 2019-2023. The goal is to evaluate the effectiveness of existing policies and strategies and identify opportunities for improvement and refinement. The ESP 2019-2023 outlines priority areas and strategies for enhancing education in Uzbekistan. By conducting a detailed ESA, the government will gain insights into the progress made and the challenges faced in implementing these priorities. Uzbekistan, situated in Central Asia, is a doubly landlocked country comprising 12 regions (provinces), an autonomous republic known as the Republic of Karakalpakstan, and a separate city, Tashkent. Approximately 51% of its 34.6 million inhabitants reside in urban areas. With a Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of US\$58 billion in 2021 and a per capita GDP of US\$17513, Uzbekistan falls under the lower-middle-income category as per the World Bank classification.

Characterized by a steadily growing population, Uzbekistan experiences an annual population growth rate of 1.48 percent. Projections indicate that the population will continue to rise in the coming decades, reaching an estimated 44.4 million by 2070. According to data from the UN Population Database, the total dependency ratio in Uzbekistan was recorded at 97.9 per 100 in 2020.

Uzbekistan Total population

2000	24,356,383
2005	25,774,623
2010	27,538,937
2015	29,681,701
2019	33,375,800
2025	35,146,618
2030	36,712,272
2035	38,059,266

As outlined in a UNICEF report from 2018, Uzbekistan currently benefits from an early demographic dividend stage, with an expected duration of approximately 30 years. However, the realization of this demographic dividend hinges upon investments in human capital development, particularly in the realms of education and skills enhancement.

With such support, the government has been able to provide quality preschool education to almost 2 million children in the age group of 3-6 years by early 2022².

Trends in Early Childhood Education 2015-2022

Girls
Boys

LITERATURE REVIEW

Vygotsky (1978, 1994) published many works on sociocultural theory with later translations summarizing his substantial contributions to constructivism. He held a strong conviction that, “human learning presupposes a specific nature and a process by which children grow into the intellectual life of those around them”³.

A recent contribution by Smagorinsky, Hansen, and Fink (2013) interpreted his words to mean that a learner’s emotions inspire thoughts, which in turn creates new knowledge. Humans are inherently social beings that coexist with others by sharing similar cultural values. Although the diversity of communities around the world can vary greatly, they all share the needs for common sociocultural learning in order to live, grow, and prosper. These learning needs are not exclusive and extend to all students⁴.

Education systems worldwide are typically well-structured, with an emphasis on the societal benefits of having an educated population. Governments, as the primary providers of education, regulate educational systems to ensure equal opportunities, quality, and positive outcomes for all children. Governments have observed that providing education is best suited to their capabilities, as they can ensure equitable access and prevent education from being solely profit-driven if left to the private sector.

Research by Tooley and Dixon (2005) has revealed the presence of private schools in unexpected locations, such as slum areas in Asia and Africa. Despite the availability of free government schooling, some parents opt to pay for private education due to perceived benefits. Lewin (2008) notes a growing demand for private education in sub-Saharan Africa, partly fueled by parental dissatisfaction with government schools. Phillipson (2008) highlights differences between government and private schools, suggesting that private institutions often offer better quality education and greater parental choice⁵.

METHODOLOGY

This analysis will serve as a crucial foundation for developing targeted interventions and shaping the new Education Programme to address current needs and aspirations in the education sector. Overall, the ESA will play a pivotal role in guiding the government’s efforts to advance education in Uzbekistan, ensuring that policies and strategies are evidence-based, responsive to emerging trends, and aligned with national development priorities. Through a collaborative and data-driven approach, the ESA will support the creation of a more inclusive, equitable, and quality education system that empowers all citizens to thrive and contribute to the country’s sustainable development.

2 [https://www.unicef.org/uzbekistan/media/5046/file/Brief%20on%20ECE%20results%20\(eng\).pdf](https://www.unicef.org/uzbekistan/media/5046/file/Brief%20on%20ECE%20results%20(eng).pdf)

3 Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press

4 Smagorinsky, P., Hansen, M. R., & Fink, L. (2013). What does Vygotsky provide for the 21st -century language arts teacher? *Language Arts*, 90(3), 192-204.

5 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/291878676_Private_schools_for_the_poor_education_where_no_one_expects_it

RESEARCH OUTCOMES

In 2012, less than one-fifth of children aged 3-6 in Uzbekistan were enrolled in preschool programs, with significant disparities among regions. While 58% of children in Tashkent city attended preschools, only 9% did so in Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya. By 2022, the overall preschool enrollment rate increased to approximately 25% nationwide, still trailing behind other countries with similar economic statuses. Upon the establishment of the Ministry of Preschool Education (MOPSE), a lack of mechanisms to assess preschool education quality led to a focus on boosting participation rather than ensuring quality. This was exacerbated by the absence of a robust Education Management Information System (EMIS) or Education Quality Assurance System (EQAS) for preschool education. As of early 2022, over 1.6 million children aged 3-6 were enrolled in preschools, with state-run preschools comprising the majority of enrollments. Notably, significant improvements were observed in SDG Indicator 4.2.2, with around 77% of 6-year-olds attending preschool in 2022 compared to 66% in 2020. Despite overall progress, regional disparities persist, particularly in Surkhandarya and Kashkadarya. Gender and socioeconomic inequalities also impact preschool participation, with children from poorer households and those with lower-educated parents less likely to attend. Addressing these disparities is crucial to ensuring equitable access to quality preschool education across Uzbekistan. Since its establishment in September 2017, the Ministry of Preschool Education in Uzbekistan has implemented various reforms aimed at improving the preschool education sector. Drawing insights from both local context and international practices, MOPSE developed a new Law on Preschool Education in December 2019, outlining the vision, goals, roles, responsibilities, and rights within the sector. These reforms included the introduction of Public-Private Partnership (PPP) models, curriculum revisions, and initiatives to enhance the status and salaries of preschool teachers⁶.

Additionally, MOPSE has made strides in enhancing technological infrastructure within state preschools, with 88% of them now equipped with computers and 93% connected to the internet. The proactive efforts of MOPSE have also attracted funding from international agencies, such as the World Bank’s “Promoting Early Childhood Development Project,” currently being implemented with a budget of US\$73.85 million.

In terms of monitoring and knowledge management, efforts have been made to improve the Education Management Information System (EMIS). Prior to 2018, data collection was fragmented, and there was a lack of unified monitoring systems. UNICEF conducted an analysis highlighting these limitations and provided technical support to pilot the OpenVMS platform for education data collection. However, technical inadequacies and limitations were identified. The development of these standards aligns with global practices and recommendations, acknowledging the pivotal role of teachers in maintaining education quality and continuity. The standards outline key competencies required for effective teaching, including education planning, teaching strategies, learning assessment, professional development, and collaboration with families. They emphasize a holistic approach to child development, taking into account individuality, rights, and early childhood development principles. During 2020-2021, MOPSE, with UNICEF support, piloted the Teacher Professional Standards (TPS)

6 [https://www.unicef.org/uzbekistan/media/5046/file/Brief%20on%20ECE%20results%20\(eng\).pdf](https://www.unicef.org/uzbekistan/media/5046/file/Brief%20on%20ECE%20results%20(eng).pdf)

in preschools across several regions, including Bukhara, Namangan, Syrdarya, and Tashkent city. UNICEF is also assisting in revising teacher attestation mechanisms and evaluation criteria to align with the TPS and international best practices. Additionally, efforts are underway to review and revise both pre-service and in-service teacher training curricula for preschool educators, considering the needs of preschool curriculum implementation and drawing lessons from global experiences.

UNICEF has played a significant role in bolstering the monitoring system for Education Quality Assurance (EQA) in Uzbekistan by supporting the State Inspectorate for the Supervision of Education Quality (SISEQ) in developing web-based platforms for QA data collection and management, namely ONAKS and an online accreditation register. These platforms have been successfully launched and are operational across all regions of Uzbekistan. However, ongoing enhancement of these systems requires thorough analysis of their implementation, identification of challenges at various levels, and capacity building for specialists to effectively analyze collected data.

In terms of research and evaluation in the preschool education sector, UNICEF conducted two targeted studies to address supply and demand side issues. The first study focused on understanding the Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices (KAP) of parents towards Early Childhood Education (ECE), revealing insights into factors influencing parents' decisions regarding preschool enrollment and highlighting gaps in their understanding of child development milestones. It assessed how young children were cared for at home, indicating increased parental engagement in childcare activities but persisting challenges, such as limited paternal involvement and stress experienced by children due to disruptions in their routines. Several achievements and enabling factors have contributed to strengthening the preschool education system in Uzbekistan:

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Overall, while significant progress has been made, ongoing efforts are needed to address remaining challenges and further enhance the quality and accessibility of preschool education in Uzbekistan. The initiatives within this strategic domain aim to ensure that preschool environments are child-friendly, inclusive, and safe, with particular attention to being sensitive to disabilities and gender. The proposed activities include enhancing or constructing preschool facilities to align with child-friendly standards, providing training for preschool educators on teaching methods to raise children's awareness about disaster risk management and safe conduct during emergencies, and educating them on crime prevention and safeguarding against violence and abuse, including gender-based violence in various settings such as schools, homes, and the community.

It's crucial, especially for preschools in remote rural areas, to have appropriate facilities that prioritize safety and create conducive learning environments. This entails measures like securing preschool premises with boundary walls, ensuring access to clean drinking water, maintaining gender-specific functional toilets and handwashing facilities, establishing playgrounds, setting up kitchen and dining areas, and providing heating facilities. Furthermore, efforts should be made to make preschools more accessible for children with disabilities and special needs, fostering an inclusive atmosphere for children from diverse backgrounds. Early engagement of children in understanding disaster risk management, safe behaviors, and violence prevention is essential. Given that teachers play a pivotal role in imparting such knowledge, preschool educators will receive training to deliver age-appropriate lessons and activities aimed at instilling these concepts effectively.

Reference:

1. UNICEF (2022): Student Learning at primary grades in Uzbekistan: Outcomes, Challenges, and Opportunities.
2. UNICEF Best of UNICEF Research (BOUR) (2020) What factors are associated with positive primary education outcomes in Uzbekistan.
3. Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
4. Smagorinsky, P., Hansen, M. R., & Fink, L. (2013). What does Vygotsky provide for the 21st-century language arts teacher? *Language Arts*, 90(3), 192-204.
5. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/291878676_Private_schools_for_the_poor_education_where_no_one_expects_it.
6. UNICEF (2018): "Generation 2030 Uzbekistan: Investing in Children and young people to reap the demographic dividend".
7. UNICEF Uzbekistan UNESCO, World Bank, UNICEF and GPE (2014):
8. Education Sector Analysis, Methodological Guidelines Volume 1. UNICEF (2020).
9. Parents' and Caretakers' Knowledge, Attitudes and Practices (KAP) towards Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) in Uzbekistan.
10. UNICEF Uzbekistan UNICEF (2020): A Rapid Assessment of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene (WASH) in schools in Uzbekistan. UNICEF Uzbekistan.

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Jtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Xondamir Ismoilov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2024. № 4

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.

Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

El.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77)

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77) telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

